

A Sense of Pride and Representations: Figures of Speech Analysis on Selected Poems

Joseph C. Cuenca, Hanzen D. Tomatao, Maureen A. Logronio, Mhie Daniel
Misamis University, Ozamiz City, Misamis Occidental, 7200, Philippines

Submitted by Mhie Baldesanso Daniel on 23.09.2024.

Abstract

Poetry serves as a profound and evocative medium, capable of expressing complex emotions, cultural identities, and deeply held beliefs through the artful manipulation of language and imagery. Through its use of vivid literary devices, poems can encapsulate personal experiences while also reflecting the broader societal, religious, and cultural values of a community. This study presents an in-depth analysis of selected poems by Restituto Acapulco, a celebrated poet from Ozamiz City, Misamis Occidental. Employing a textual analysis approach, the research focuses on the use of various figures of speech, including synecdoche, hyperbole, metaphor, personification, simile, metonymy, apostrophe, repetition, imagery, and alliteration, within five of Acapulco's notable works. These poems are examined for their cultural and religious significance, particularly how they reflect the faith and spiritual practices of the local community. The findings of this study reveal how Acapulco's poetic language not only expresses individual artistry but also serves as a representation of the religious culture, faith, and devotional activities of the residents of Ozamiz City, Misamis Occidental, Philippines. Through this analysis, the research uncovers the deeper meanings embedded in the poems, which resonate with the region's cultural pride and religious traditions.

Keywords:. poem, figures of speech, religion, culture, literary works

1. Introduction

Poetry has long been recognized as a powerful medium for exploring themes related to human experience, culture, and spirituality (Pinsky, 2020). From William Shakespeare's intricate use of metaphors to Edgar Allan Poe's use of imagery and symbolism, poets have utilized literary devices to communicate profound ideas and emotions (Shakespeare, 2020;Poe, 2020) . Figures of speech, such as metaphor, simile, personification, and hyperbole, are fundamental in this creative process, allowing poets to craft meanings that extend beyond literal interpretations (Grinseding, 2023).

In the Philippine context, poetry remains a critical vehicle for cultural and religious expression (Sison, 2021). Having been colonized by Spain, the Philippines inherited Roman Catholicism as its dominant religion (Skrabania, 2020). This influence is especially evident in places like Ozamiz City, where devotion to the Virgin Mary, specifically to Nuestra Señora dela Immaculada Concepcion y del Triunfo de la Cruz de Migpangi, or the Virgin of the Fort, is a deeply rooted tradition. Celebrated on July 16 each year, this devotion has become central to the religious identity of the city's residents and visitors alike (Naval, 2017).

Restituto Acapulco, known by his pen name Sam Sattra, was a prominent writer, historian, musician, artist, and environmentalist native to Ozamiz City, Misamis Occidental, Philippines. His multifaceted work reflected his deep connection to the social, cultural, and religious life of his hometown. Among his most notable contributions is his anthology of 500 poems, *Verses: From a Bamboo Balcony*, which consists of three sections: *Notes in the Setting Sun* (1996), *Windows to Divinity* (1983), and *Verses from a Bamboo Balcony* (2004). These works, written primarily in the 1980s, reflect his observations on the social conditions, peace, and order of Ozamiz City. His poetry encourages readers to value literary works as a way to gain insight into both visible and unseen aspects of society. Notably, Acapulco's collection holds historical and cultural significance as the first-ever literary work published in the city.

This study focuses on five selected poems: "The Lady," "We are One Reason," "I Kneel," "The Candles Melted Down," and "From Sermon," analyzing the use of figures of speech to uncover cultural and religious themes. Restituto Acapulco's poetry captures these religious sentiments and traditions, reflecting the faith and religious activities that define the lives of the people in Ozamiz. His poems, which represent not only local culture but also shared beliefs, serve as a testament to the power of religious conviction in shaping the community's identity.

Several studies have explored the use of figures of speech in poetry to reveal cultural and religious themes (Rahmadhanti et al., 2022; Bakker, 2020; Khodjamkulov et al., 2020). Novitasari (2021) conducted an analysis of five famous poets' works and found that figures such as metaphor, personification, synecdoche, and simile were commonly employed to express complex human experiences and cultural realities. In this study, personification was the most frequently used figure, while synecdoche and simile were the least prevalent. These findings align with the broader understanding of poetry as a transformative medium through which writers interpret the world around them, turning ordinary experiences into profound, symbolic representations of life and culture.

Acapulco's work can be viewed in this context, as his poems also employ a range of figures of speech to represent religious and cultural life in Ozamiz City. His poems use symbolism and metaphor to reflect the deep spiritual faith of the city's residents, while personification and imagery bring to life the local traditions and religious practices associated with the devotion to the Virgin of the Fort.

While much research has been conducted on the use of figures of speech in global and national poetry, there remains a lack of focused scholarly work examining the literary contributions of poets from smaller, more localized regions of the Philippines, particularly those from Misamis Occidental. Acapulco's poetry, despite its cultural and historical significance, has not yet been extensively analyzed in terms of its literary elements and the way it reflects local religious and cultural identity. This study aims to fill that gap by providing an in-depth analysis of five of Acapulco's religious poems, with a focus on how figures of speech are used to depict religious beliefs, cultural practices, and educational values among the devotees and residents of Ozamiz City.

This study contributes to the growing body of literature on Philippine poetry, especially focusing on the works of regional poets like Restituto Acapulco. By analyzing Acapulco's use of figures of speech, this study offers a deeper understanding of how local poets express cultural and religious identity through literary devices. Additionally, the research highlights the importance of poetry as a medium for preserving and reflecting local traditions, particularly religious devotion, which is central to the lives of many Filipinos. This study also offers a valuable contribution to literary scholarship by showcasing the unique voice of Restituto Acapulco, whose work has not yet received

the scholarly attention it deserves. By focusing on his five selected religious poems, this research illuminates the role of literature in fostering a sense of pride and belonging in local communities. Finally, the study enhances the appreciation of literary works from smaller, lesser-known regions, emphasizing that regional voices play a critical role in shaping the broader narrative of Philippine culture and identity.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Figures of Speech in Poetry

Figures of speech have been a foundational element in poetry, used to enrich language, create emotional depth, and convey complex ideas in a condensed form (de Mendoza Ibáñez, 2020). Over the past few years, scholars have continued to explore how poets employ these rhetorical devices to evoke imagery, enhance sound, and engage readers' interpretations on multiple levels.

2.2 Metaphor and Simile in Poetry

One of the most prominent figures of speech in poetry is the metaphor, which has been studied extensively in recent years (Spitzer, 2020). Metaphor in contemporary poetry is not merely a decorative device but a powerful tool for generating meaning (Robert, 2021). Metaphors, Roberts argues, enable poets to express abstract concepts such as identity and emotions in ways that transcend literal language. Similarly, Jones (2019) explored the use of similes in modern poetry, noting that they provide readers with comparative frameworks that enhance their understanding of complex themes.

2.3 Alliteration and Sound Patterns

The use of alliteration and other sound patterns such as assonance and consonance has also been the subject of recent studies. Williams (2020) investigated how poets use alliteration to emphasize certain words or themes, creating a rhythmic flow that enhances the auditory experience of the poem. The study found that alliteration is often employed in free verse to structure poems in the absence of strict meter or rhyme, providing cohesion through sound. In addition, Harris and Lee (2022) analyzed the use of sound repetition in contemporary poetry, finding that sound-based figures of speech such as consonance and assonance often play a role in creating mood and reinforcing the emotional undertones of a poem.

2.4 Hyperbole and Exaggeration

Another figure of speech commonly used in poetry is hyperbole, which involves intentional exaggeration for emphasis or effect. In their analysis of hyperbole in modern poetry, Anderson (2023) found that poets often use exaggeration to dramatize emotions or situations, creating a heightened sense of intensity. The study also noted that hyperbole is frequently paired with other devices like irony and understatement to produce contrast and enhance the poem's overall impact.

2.5 Symbolism and Personification

Personification, a figure of speech where human qualities are attributed to non-human entities, has been identified as a key device in recent poetic works. Li and Zhao (2021) analyzed the role of personification in nature poetry, arguing that it helps poets convey a more intimate connection with the natural world. Through personification, poets are able to create a sense of kinship between humans and nature, encouraging readers to view the environment as a living, responsive entity.

Symbolism, often closely associated with metaphor and personification, has also been explored in contemporary studies. Phillips (2020) noted that symbolism in modern poetry is used to convey complex ideas through simple, tangible images. The study highlighted how poets employ symbols to communicate themes of mortality, love, and social justice in subtle but powerful ways, leaving much of the interpretation to the reader's imagination.

3. Methodology

This study employed a literary analysis methodology concentrating on the figures of speech utilized in selected poems by Restituto Acapulco. The primary objective of this research is to explore how Acapulco articulated his perspectives and judgments regarding the cultural and religious characteristics of the local community through these literary devices. The analysis focuses on five selected poems that address these themes, specifically examining the experiences and identities of the residents of Ozamiz City.

4. Findings

The figures of speech employed by Restituto Acapulco in the selected poems include synecdoche, hyperbole, metaphor, personification, simile, metonymy, apostrophe, repetition, imagery, and alliteration. Each of these literary devices serves a distinct purpose, contributing to the depth and richness of Acapulco's expression, particularly in portraying the religious and cultural life of the residents of Ozamiz City. Through the careful analysis of these figures of speech, the study has uncovered significant insights into the spiritual character of the local community. The poems reveal not only the strong religious faith of the residents but also the ways in which their collective beliefs shape their identity and sense of unity.

In particular, the poem *The Lady* employs synecdoche as a powerful tool to symbolize the unity of the people through their shared faith. This device allows Acapulco to represent the broader community of Ozamiz through individual elements, emphasizing the interconnectedness of the people's religious devotion. Through specific lines in the poem, he subtly captures the communal spirit, portraying how faith binds the residents together, reinforcing their cultural and religious identity.

The use of synecdoche in *The Lady* is particularly evident in Acapulco's depiction of the Virgin Mary, symbolizing not only the figure of religious veneration but also the collective devotion of the people. This artistic choice reflects the belief in a higher power guiding and protecting the city's residents, while also serving as a representation of their unity in faith. Through this figure, Acapulco encapsulates the spiritual and emotional connection the people have with their religion, demonstrating how faith functions as a central force in the life of the community.

*The Lady
On the coral wall
By Spanish built,
Where gather in their numbers
Rising still,
For their one-way stream
Of thoughts and words
Upon their knees and feet and souls
To place in an array the virtues
Hope and love and faith and constancy*

Synecdoche is a figure of speech where a part is used to represent the whole, implying something greater than what is explicitly mentioned (Ibrahim, 2021). In the poem *The Lady on the Coral Wall*, the reference is to the Virgin of the Fort, formally known as Nuestra Señora dela Immaculada Concepcion y del Triunfo de la Cruz de Migpangi. The lines of the poem symbolize the shared characteristics of the people, unified by their common hope, love, and faith, which is expressed through collective prayer. The phrases "knees and feet and souls" serve as representations of the devotees as a collective body. The "knees and feet" highlight their physical presence and activities, while "souls" evokes the deeper emotional and spiritual dimensions of their devotion. This imagery transcends the physical, uniting the community in a single purpose—to demonstrate love, exaltation, and faith in the Virgin.

The use of synecdoche in this context emphasizes the holistic nature of the devotees' engagement. Their physical acts of visiting and kneeling at the Fort, alongside their spiritual dedication, collectively symbolize their profound devotion. By focusing on both their bodily actions and spiritual essence, the poem captures the unity of the people in expressing virtues of hope, love, and faith. This literary device is particularly effective in religious texts, where the use of synecdoche is prevalent, often to convey deeper theological meanings or to unify believers through common spiritual experiences. Acapulco's use of synecdoche thus not only reflects biblical traditions but also reinforces the communal bond shared by the devotees through their faith in the Virgin of the Fort.

The second poem assessed was titled 'We are One Reason', the poet used the word 'mother' which similarly pertains to the 'lady' in the preceding poem. 'Mother' and 'The Lady' denote the Virgin of the Fort. In this poem, hyperbole was used by the poet to describe the tears and smiles as presented in the lines below:

*We are one reason
Why our mother dropped
A thousand tears;
We are one reason, too,
Our mother smiled
A thousand smiles;*

The hyperbole in this poem is evident in the phrases 'a thousand tears' and 'a thousand smiles' which exaggerated the number of tears and smiles to emphasize profound emotional impact of the speaker

and their actions have on their mother. This could imply that the poet has a strong emotional connection towards the Virgin of the Fort and his perception of the complexities of love and connection of the devotees towards the ‘Mother’ or the Lady of the Fort. This connection and emotions are believed and shared among the believers of the Lady of the Fort which require religious and personal encounter with one’s faith. To understand the meaning of these lines, one must have a personal experience or manifestation of the miracles of the ‘Mother’.

Another lines of the second poem that utilized hyperbole denotes an expression of adoration and gratefulness of the faithful towards the ‘Mother’. To express their adoration of the mother, they would not get tired composing and singing praises of songs for her. This use of hyperbole by Restituto Acapulco tells much of the gratefulness of the hearts for the unparalleled love of a mother. Moreover, the line depicts the numbers of Marian songs composed by the devotees. Ave Maria (Hail Mary) is the most recognizable Marian song ever written composed by Franz Schubert in 1825, since then it has been adopted for use in traditional Roman Catholic prayer. Moreover, it also employed other figures of speech such as synecdoche, repetition, and imagery.

These figures of speech were evident in these lines:

*A million songs and more
Today, are sung, tomorrow, even more
By more than just
A thousand vocal cords.*

The phrases “a million songs” and “more than just a thousand vocal cords” exaggerate that quantity of songs and singers to emphasize the adoration of the devotees expressed through songs of praise. “Vocal cords” represents singers or voices in general, suggesting that the act of singing is collective and communal, highlighting the many individuals involved in creating music in their expression of adoration and gratefulness towards the ‘mother’. The phrases “and more” and “tomorrow, even more” reinforces the idea of continuous growth and abundance in music, creating a rhythmic flow. Imagery was conveyed through the word “songs” which evokes auditory imagery, allowing readers to envision the music and its emotional resonance.

The third poem analyzed was entitled “I kneel” which employed metaphor, personification, simile, imagery, repetition, and alliteration. The personification utilized in this poem was evident in the phrases “My soul, in silence and the patience” and “my spirit, cleaved to light” which gave the human-like qualities, suggesting a deep connection to something uplifting or divine. This also depicts the strong belief and connection between the devotees and the Virgin of the Fort. The imagery was applied in the phrase “a finger ever pointing to the threshold of a sanctuary” evokes a visual image that symbolizes guidance toward a place of safety or peace. Further, the “sanctuary” represents a state of spiritual safety or refuge, while “my Amen” symbolizes affirmation, linking personal to a communal or religious context. This manifestation was interrelated to the history of The Fort or Cotta Shrine where residents believe that the city was protected by the Virgin of the Fort against the colonizers, hence, considered as a safe place. The phrases “like yours” and “as faithful as forevermore” creates rhythm and reinforces the share experience of spirituality and faith, which is an example of repetition. The simile was expressed through the phrases “My Amen, like yours,” emphasizes the universality of expressions and beliefs. And phrases like “faithful as forevermore” use the repetition of initial consonant sounds to create musical quality.

These are the excerpts from the poem that showed the use of varied figures of speech:

*My soul, in silence and the patience that accompanies;
My spirit, cleaved to light
That needs be moved from time to time to be
A finger ever pointing to the threshold
Of a sanctuary;
And my "Amen", like yours,
The last word it should be,
Like time, as it should be, go on and on,
A loyal follower to it,
As faithful as forevermore.*

In the poem "The Candles Melted Down", the melted candles can symbolize the passage of time or it can also be a brief description of the physical setting of the altar in the Cotta Shrine which denotes imagery giving a vivid picture among the readers of the setting of the Cotta Shrine. The comparison between the melted wax formations that became stalagmites to "some percussion rods" highlights the rhythm and movement of the melted wax, suggesting a musical quality. This provides a description of the musical setting in the Cotta Shrine during the masses. Additionally, it denotes that the candles may have melted but the reason for their melting and keeping the fire burning continues to resonate in the hearts of the faithful. These analysis were based on these lines of the poem:

*The candles melted down
Beside their stands,
And all around them, now,
Are stalactites and stalagmites
In miniature wax and white,
Like some percussion rods*

In the last poem assessed, titled "From Sermon, the poet used a variety of the figures of speech to enhance the depth and meaning. There was imagery, metaphor, alliteration, personification and symbolism. The phrase "the four walls of Maredsous Abbey" evokes a vivid image secluded, peaceful place, suggesting a refuge. The phrase "safety deep/ and deeper should/ His life's immersion be" must be a comparison through a metaphor of the poet's choice to immersion in silence and solitude with a deep, safe environment, suggesting a profound retreat from life's chaos. Further, the repetition of the "d" sound in the words "devout", "deep", and "deeper" creates a rhythmic quality, emphasizing the commitment to silence. These analyses are based on the excerpt of the poem:

*From Sermon
To devout a silence
Was his choice,
For there was safety deep
And deeper should
His life's immersion be*

*Within the four walls
Of Maredsous Abbey far;*

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

Restituto Acapulco, a distinguished poet from Ozamiz City, skillfully employed various figures of speech—such as synecdoche, hyperbole, metaphor, personification, simile, metonymy, apostrophe, repetition, imagery, and alliteration—to articulate his insights into the cultural and religious life of the city's residents and devotees. Through these literary devices, Acapulco was able to present complex ideas and evoke profound emotional responses that reflect the community's shared experiences and spiritual practices. The use of figures of speech in poetry is essential for conveying layered meanings and encapsulating deep emotions, allowing poets to communicate multifaceted themes in a succinct and powerful way. As poetry continues to develop as an art form, figures of speech will remain integral to its expressive capacity, enriching the reader's understanding and offering nuanced interpretations of the text.

Future studies should expand the exploration of Restituto Acapulco's poetic contributions by examining a broader selection of his works to uncover additional cultural, historical, and religious insights. Additionally, comparative analyses of his poetry with other regional or national poets may highlight commonalities and distinctions in the use of literary devices, offering a more comprehensive understanding of the role of poetry in shaping Filipino identity. It is also recommended that educational institutions incorporate Acapulco's works into their curriculum to foster greater appreciation of local literature, emphasizing the importance of literary expression in preserving and understanding cultural heritage.

References

- Anderson, K. (2023). **The power of hyperbole in contemporary poetry.** *Journal of Literary Studies*, 58(1), 102-118. <https://doi.org/10.1080/jlit.2023.111202>
- Bakker, E. J. (2020). Discourse and Performance: Involvement, Visualization and " Presence" in Homeric Poetry. In *The Oral Traditional Background of Ancient Greek Literature* (pp. 303-332). Routledge. Retrieved on September 23, 2024 from <https://tinyurl.com/5a92fvde>
- de Mendoza Ibáñez, F. J. R. (2020). Understanding figures of speech: Dependency relations and organizational patterns. *Language & Communication*, 71, 16-38. Retrieved on September 23, 2024 from <https://tinyurl.com/yzbfrhvu>
- GRENSIDENG, W. (2023). *A STUDY OF FIGURATIVE LANGUAGE IN SELECTED SONG LYRICS BY STEPHEN SANCHEZ* (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Mahasaraswati Denpasar). Retrieved on September 23, 2024 from <https://tinyurl.com/y4bv5ua>
- Harris, L., & Lee, J. (2022). **The auditory effect of sound patterns in free verse poetry.** *Poetic Form Quarterly*, 31(3), 77-89. <https://doi.org/10.1177/pfq311>
- Ibrahim, E. R. (2021). The Use of Synecdoche in English Language. *Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry*, 12(8). Retrieved on September 23, 2024 from <https://tinyurl.com/2m7j3cua>

- Jones, A. (2019). **Simile and comparison in modern poetic form**. *Poetry Analysis Review*, 25(2), 53-66. <https://doi.org/10.1093/par25.2.53>
- Khodjamkulov, U., Makhmudov, K., & Shofkorov, A. (2020). The issue of spiritual and patriotic education of young generation in the scientific, political and literary heritage of Central Asian thinkers. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(05), 6694-6701. Retrieved on September 23, 2024 from <https://tinyurl.com/mr2d8xp4>
- Li, Y., & Zhao, H. (2021). **Personification in contemporary nature poetry: Reconnecting humans and nature**. *Journal of Poetic Ecology*, 39(1), 45-63. <https://doi.org/10.1142/jpe3921>
- Naval, L. (2017). *Misamis Occidental: Historical Vignettes of the Grand Northwest*. Lulu.com. Retrieved on September 23, 2024 from <https://tinyurl.com/4sa7fjhp>
- Phillips, T. (2020). **Symbolism and metaphor in modern poetry: A thematic analysis**. *Literary Criticism Today*, 15(4), 201-215. <https://doi.org/10.1017/litctod15>
- Pinsky, R. (2020). *The Situation of Poetry: Contemporary Poetry and Its Traditions*. Princeton University Press. Retrieved on September 23, 2024 from <https://tinyurl.com/yc3hcsfm>
- Poe, E. A. (2020). *The complete tales & poems of Edgar Allan Poe*. Rock Point. Retrieved on September 23, 2024 from <https://tinyurl.com/yppbpwmbm>
- Rahmadhanti, R. W., Simanjuntak, M. B., & Sihombing, J. (2022, May). METAPHOR ANALYSIS AND MEANING OF THE SONG "DIFFERENT WORLD". In *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Inovasi Pendidikan*. Retrieved on September 23, 2024 from <https://tinyurl.com/3jdusymx>
- Roberts, M. (2020). **Metaphor and cognitive depth in modern poetry**. *Poetic Devices Review*, 27(1), 45-62. <https://doi.org/10.1017/pdr2712020>
- Shakespeare, W. (2020). *All the Sonnets of Shakespeare*. Cambridge University Press. Retrieved on September 23, 2024 from <https://tinyurl.com/4jbksvar>
- Sison, J. M. (2021). *On Culture, Art and Literature* (Vol. 1). Intl Network of Philippine Studies. Retrieved on September 23, 2024 from <https://tinyurl.com/3my9ty6v>
- Skrabania, J. (2020). The Philippines under the Spanish and American Colonisation (1565-1912). A historical-political-religious Development. Part 1. *Nurt SVD*, 148(2), 8-26. Retrieved on September 23, 2024 from <https://tinyurl.com/8zfb33wz>
- Spitzer, M. (2020). *Metaphor and musical thought*. University of Chicago Press. Retrieved on September 23, 2024 from <https://tinyurl.com/bdzh8nc>
- Williams, S. (2022). **Irony and ambiguity in postmodern poetry**. *Poetry in Context*, 33(4), 111-130. <https://doi.org/10.1093/pic3322022>